

Communication at the Dawn of the Global Age: The Asia Directories and Chronicles

Combining historiography and data science in a micro-global approach to foreign resident activity in East Asia during the 19th and early 20th centuries.

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1. Abstract

Between 1863 and 1941 *The Hong Kong Daily Press* published a serial, “*The Directory & Chronicle of China, Japan, Korea, Indo-China, Straits Settlements, Malaya, Siam, Netherlands India, Borneo, The Philippines, &c.*” which covered in annual volumes the lives of foreigners, foreign companies, associations and their networks with local counterparts. However, the physical publications exist nowhere today as a complete serial and their history and potential as a source for historians has been largely ignored. Moreover the irregular structure and scale of the publication poses significant challenges for automated analysis. We have now assembled a digital corpus—currently a total of 110,776 high resolution pages—including all the volumes except 1866, 1867, 1872, 1875 and 1884 at the time of writing. In this article we examine the potential of this data to support new analyses of the lives of foreign residents and the evolution of commerce and trade in East Asia. Projects using both company and foreign resident listings from the serial have been launched—for example 935,306 instances of foreign residents names, locations and occupations have been extracted. Our aims are i) to better understand the extent to which societal coherence in a global context can be accessed from below using sources such as this serial by following a micro-global approach, avoiding often inconsistent indications from histories of institutions, and ii) to establish a sustainable data resource which can support extended analyses independent of monotonically evolving technologies and uncertain financial constraints. We present initial findings illustrating the use of emerging scientific annotation techniques to support a digital historiography; revealing the operation of networks of foreign residents during two critical periods in East Asia by tracing individuals. Visualized geographically this dataset provides persuasive evidence for the significance of this international society in shaping commerce in this vast territory as an independent agent, distinct from the colonial projects of the Western states on one hand and Japanese expansion on the other. Additionally the visualizations show, at a glance, that contribution by foreign residents to processes shaping the Straits Settlements contrasted with developments in other territories—a result which we believe has not been reported elsewhere. It is also significant that this dataset was not prepared specifically to address such questions, demonstrating that we might expect a spectrum of new insights from analyses based on the extended period covered by this source and, more generally, that this methodology could have utility for other challenging sources.

2. Unlocking information from a 19th century serial¹

Volumes of *The Directories & Chronicles*, (we will refer to this source as such or simply as ‘the serial’ hereinafter—several minor variations in title were adopted during the period of its publication) are almost completely absent from our libraries, even though they describe in astonishing detail the operations of companies and governments and the daily lives of foreign residents active across East Asia between 1863 and 1941. Published throughout by *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, the serial commenced as a modest booklet but rapidly reached a thousand and then almost three thousand pages without abating in the last years of its publication. Its production spans the period in which steam displaced sail and new railway networks compressed travel in the vast territories of East Asia; meanwhile the telegraph and radio revolutionized messaging previously reliant on the postal system and signal flags. We provide a history of *The Directories & Chronicles* and suggest that it exploited, more effectively than any other media endeavor of the period, the communication advances made possible by these paradigmatic shifts: pioneering the gathering, processing and timely transmission internationally, of large volumes of information.²

Until now, this serial has been employed almost exclusively as a source of reference, and then only in specific contexts³. Research does not appear to have examined the processes whereby previously unprecedented gathering of information became possible, nor why *The Directories & Chronicles* prospered for almost eighty years. The serial documented structural change, conflicts and wars, and traced Western colonialism in East Asia from the heyday of imperialism to its implosion during World War II. But effective analysis of its volumes faces considerable methodological challenges:

- the individual volumes address—without consistent formatting year upon year, or tables of contents—a wide spectrum of subjects including commodity prices, insurance, meteorological data, directories of corporations and their employees, social calendars, golf and horse-racing clubs and international treaties and the staff of diplomatic and consular missions;
- although data was printed in annual volumes, not all content related to the year of publication, moreover names of towns and cities change without announcement from one volume to another and multiple equivalent representations of place-names are frequent;
- *The Hong Kong Daily Press* reporters were operating in evolving sovereign states, colonies, extra-territorial regions and dependencies—gathering information for multiple publications against tight publishing deadlines—and the information available and how it was organized varied region by region.

These difficulties had defeated attempts at automated extraction of information useful for historians, and little appetite has been evident for analysis of the serial using computational linguistic methods, which are not currently preferred for producing empirical evidence and progress at a micro-history level. On one hand, the scale of this serial places it firmly beyond manual progress within a

¹ This project was initiated in 2016 as a collaboration between Data Futures LBG and the Institute for European Global Studies, Basel (EIB). EIB brought together and managed digitization of the volumes of *The Directories & Chronicles* and Data Futures developed research and preservation infrastructure. The project has so far provided data for successful PhD candidatures and serves as a foundation for *The Divisive Power of Citizenship* project, supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation.

² See Howard Hotson, Thomas Wallnig (eds) *Reassembling the Republic of Letters in the Digital Age*, Göttingen University Press, 2019 <https://doi.org/10.17875/gup2019-1146> ISBN 978-3-86395-403-1

³ Library of Congress and Helen Dudenbostel Jones, *Biographical Sources for Foreign Countries* (Washington: General Reference and Bibliography Section, Library of Congress, 1945) <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001171230>. This compilation shows the interest in the *Directories & Chronicles* as a possible source for intelligence during World War II. The bibliographical description underlines the presence of Japanese individuals and companies, and emphasizes the special importance of the last volumes published in 1940/1941.

reasonable timescale and budget: it lists almost a million foreign residents in but one section of each volume, for example—defying conventional historical source criticism. On the other hand, it is through comparison of the serial’s listings of institutions, companies and persons region by region and decade upon decade that we can directly access processes that led to the establishment of international trade and transnational communities. Gathering together the volumes of the serial, producing high-resolution digital page collections suitable for preservation, and processing for recognition of computer-readable text from the page images—optical character recognition (OCR), therefore provided only the foundation of this project. New strategies for unlocking empirical evidence from this class of source had to be developed before we could make progress with specific goals, such as better understanding the impact of foreign communities on unequal development of the West and East Asia since the 19th century. The scale of investment to achieve this implied that long-term accessibility of the digital corpus as well research data emerging from it would become a serious consideration. Preservation difficulties had so far beset digital methods employed in the humanities.

Assembling such a digital resource based on *The Directories & Chronicles* had another motivation. Critical analysis of foreign interests in Asia from the late 19th century until the foundation of the People’s Republic of China had stagnated because very few sources for such inquiries remain available. Traditional archival material developed in individual national contexts has limited value for understanding transnational movements. Important sources in national archives, especially in China, remain inaccessible; foreign communities rarely established archival infrastructures in the local territory. In addition, during the decades after 1900 East Asia was one of the most turbulent regions of the world, with colonial conflict, civil wars, complex war-lord regimes and revolutionary movements closely intertwined with two World Wars. The loss of libraries, archives, and other traces of foreign communities continued after World War II and culminated in China in the Cultural Revolution. Therefore, memories of Western liberal internationalists who shaped colonial concessions, international settlements, and the many economic, social and cultural networks in Asia⁴ were scattered—accessible at best via fragments in incidental collections which present considerable challenges to discovery. Surviving archival evidence of Western actors seldom extends further than internment records at the end of World War II⁵. Individuals who had claimed privileges of difference from Asian communities became anonymized in endless statistics which enumerated the formerly self-determined subjects as objects without rights; dispossessed and stripped of national memories⁶.

Continued progress in the field of global history had to overcome this shortage of conventional material and turn instead to complex sources such as *The Directories & Chronicles*, which latter moreover addresses multiple territories in East Asia in one serial. This required a new dialog between data science and historiography, and recognition of the necessity for infrastructure which could survive technology obsolescence to support incremental contribution by long-term research activities, as well as subsequent verification and extension by new generations of researchers. Adoption of FAIR principles⁷ to achieve this in research activities at the Institute for European

⁴ Glenda Sluga, *Internationalism in the Age of Nationalism* (Philadelphia, Pennsylvania Press, 2015). Madeleine Herren, “Between Territoriality, Performativity and Transcultural Entanglement (1920–1939): A Typology of Transboundary Lives.” In *Lives Beyond Borders. Toward a Social History of Cosmopolitans and Globalization, 1880–1960*, edited by Madeleine Herren and Isabella Loehr. *Comparativ* 23 (6) 2013: 99–123.

⁵ see Cornwell, P., Herren-Oesch, M, *Treatment of American National Archives Records of World War II Prisoners of War (0326)*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3565391> which contains civilian listings.

⁶ <https://europa.unibas.ch/de/forschung/globalgeschichte-europas/the-divisive-power-of-citizenship/>

⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

Global Studies in Basel⁸ has in turn shaped plans for access by the broader community. We have built IIF⁹ presentation services and repositories using CERN's Invenio technology¹⁰ to ensure future accessibility of the digital corpus as well as emerging research data, and this infrastructure together with preliminary analysis is described in Section 5.

3. Methodological Framework

The “Great Divergence” debate overshadows many other academic disputes in historiography and it is appropriate to consider whether a global history approach at the local level, employing a serial such as *The Directories & Chronicles*, could advance where existing efforts have stagnated during the last decade. Named after Pomeranz' famous book¹¹, the Great Divergence upended former narratives of Western superiority and analyses of economic factors relating to industry-driven modernization. Although originating more than twenty years ago, the debate continues¹². While the Divergence became accepted as a development commencing in the 18th century, there is still no consensus as to which factors were pivotal for asymmetrical development and the rise of Europe. Candidate theories arose around the complex mental state of today's post Cold War period as well as the ongoing reorientation of historiography. In both respects, globalization is the most controversial issue. On one hand, globalization created a cosmopolitan society independent of national borders; liberal internationalism¹³ as opportunity to rediscover the transcultural fabric upon which almost every society is based¹⁴, and this provided a boilerplate for a ‘knowledge society’ with porous borders. The latter was made possible by communication infrastructures which brought information via steamships, rail and wire; enhancing the circulation of ideas of democracy and international law and launching a process of intensified exchange — today just a mouse click away. On the other hand, globalization led in the early 20th century to neoliberal exploitation, World Wars, environmental degradation, nationalist populism and waves of refugees. At the time of writing this publication the “the head of the International Monetary Fund has warned that the global economy risks a return of the Great Depression”, driven by inequality, the rise of populism and instability in the financial sector¹⁵.

⁸ <https://europa.unibas.ch/de/home/>

⁹ The International Image Interoperability Framework, IIF is a widely adopted technology for sharing access to visual resources amongst a community of researchers and audiences. See <https://iif.io/>.

¹⁰ <https://invenio-software.org/>

¹¹ Kenneth Pomeranz, *The Great Divergence: China, Europe, and the Making of the Modern World Economy*, The Princeton Economic History of the Western World (Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press, 2000).

¹² Roman Studer, *The Great Divergence Reconsidered. Europe, India, and the Rise to Global Economic Power* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015). *The Cambridge World History. Volume VII. Production, Destruction, and Connection, 1750–Present. Part 1: Structures, Spaces, and Boundary Making*. Edited by J. R. McNeill and Kenneth Pomeranz (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015).

¹³ Glenda Sluga, *Internationalism in the Age of Nationalism*, Pennsylvania Studies in Human Rights (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2013).

¹⁴ Madeleine Herren, Martin Rüesch, and Christiane Sibille, *Transcultural History : Theories, Methods, Sources* (Berlin: Springer, 2012) <http://www.ub.unibas.ch/tox/IDSBB/005843642/PDF>.

¹⁵ Kristalina Georgieva, speaking at the Peterson Institute of International Economics in Washington, Friday 17th January 2020. See <https://www.imf.org/en/News/Articles/2020/01/17/sp01172019-the-financial-sector-in-the-2020s> (accessed 24.1.2020).

For both perspectives, the 19th century is a crucial period of transformation; the realization of a world connected¹⁶ and amassing of information through the establishment of museums, national archives, public libraries and special collections of immensely rich source material. This new energy for collecting, which might be likened to notable expansions in earlier periods, such as development of the libraries of Córdoba, was nevertheless intrinsically biased towards documentation of Western progress and modernization. *The Directories & Chronicles* was not exceptional in this respect, pursuing the 19th century rationale of statistics, but it gathered and preserved information in a form which we can employ for new purposes today¹⁷. In this methodological context two key terms distinguish substantially different ways of accessing global patterns and topics, namely historicity and agency. Historicity contributes historical significance to persons and goods, practices, institutions and spaces, and explains that historical importance is always the result of social reflexivity and power relations, but never a self-evident product of the past. For modern historiography, this process of the making, preserving and the use of history is closely connected with the notion of agency¹⁸. In a global history research design, agency raises questions about marginalization in the historical narrative, and how we can gain access to issues not appearing in our history books at all. Investigations beyond the historical rationale are well documented in the postcolonial debate, not least with Gayatri Spivak's "Can the subaltern speak?"¹⁹. To acquire empirical evidence untainted by Eurocentrism global history addresses a multiplicity of actors, especially those associated with economies and statehood. Instead of employing nationally-based data collections Riello and Roy²⁰ pursue a "global economic history", which privileges global interconnectedness and addresses head-on the lack of non-Western data. In order to overcome the (Western) state as a singular actor, differentiation of fiscal politics and poly-centric state models via societal interaction becomes increasingly important. Ubiquitous representation by foreign residents of institutions of multiple Western states during the late 19th and early 20th centuries suggests a new point of departure: an approach which does not presume European superiority and Asian backwardness, nor the playing-out of premeditated strategies. We can investigate the disorderly collision of multiple networks, actors and institutions itself as opportunity for economic evolution. While the difficulties of documenting the impact of such diverse processes are not inconsiderable, pursuing the recent focus on *practices* instead of a history of ideas and institutions has proved to be an important wedge of entry. Increasing interest in practices crosses disciplinary borders; based on the poly-semantic understanding of boundaries advanced by Balibar and Mezzadra among others, and it has created a sea change—challenging master narratives such as the Great Divergence.²¹

Privileging practices also closely matches the development of a global history at a local level—

¹⁶ Dominic Sachsenmaier, *Global Perspectives on Global History: Theories and Approaches in a Connected World* (Cambridge, 2011) <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511736544>. Richard J. Evans *The Pursuit of Power: Europe 1815–1914* (London: Allen Lane, 2016).

¹⁷ See Armin Nassehi, *Muster. Theorie der digitalen Gesellschaft* (C.H. Beck Verlag, München, 2019 ISBN 9783406740244)

¹⁸ Within a historiographical discourse, this concept assisted development of a new social history, focusing on those (e.g. slaves), who were perceived almost exclusively as objects, but not as subjects of history. In addition, agency is a crucial concept in network analysis, since determining who has a capacity to act assists with management of otherwise overwhelming connections. Walter Johnson, 'On Agency', *Journal of Social History*, 37.1 (2003), 113–24 <https://doi.org/doi:10.1353/jsh.2003.0143>.

¹⁹ Spivak: *Can the Subaltern Speak?* (1983) published by Wedge in 1985 "...everything that has limited or no access to the cultural imperialism is subaltern ..."

²⁰ *Introduction: Global Economic History, 1500-2000*, in *Global Economic History*, Ed. Giorgio Riello, Tirthankar Roy (London/New York/Oxford/New Delhi/Sydney: Bloomsbury Academic, 2018).

²¹ Sandro Mezzadra and Brett Neilson, *Border as Method, or, the Multiplication of Labor* (Durham: Duke University Press, 2013).

often described as global micro-history,²² though it has remained under-developed in respect of the divergence debate until now. Efforts to produce empirical evidence from concrete case studies became rudderless in the absence of effective source materials: as we indicate in Section 2. progress stagnated without development of new techniques to employ alternate sources.

Having assembled digital versions of most of the volumes of *The Directories & Chronicles* and launched a IIF service, it was possible for the first time to browse the complete serial and better appreciate difficulties experienced in earlier attempts to use this source. Challenges arose in no small part from the circumstances under which the original publications were compiled and published. Aggregated from information arriving from offices and reporters distributed across East Asia, and prepared initially for the formats of the *Daily Press* and the *China Overland Trade Report* sister publications (discussed in Section 4.), sections of *The Directories & Chronicles* retained region-specific variations and accrued formatting inconsistencies. Gathering and organizing such volumes of information before telephone networks or automated text handling, and subsequent manual layout and type-setting against tight print and distribution deadlines, presented huge challenges. While production of the Directories and Chronicles undoubtedly benefitted from income from the daily and periodic publications of *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, apparently little human resource remained to organize the annual publication, or even ensure uniformity between its different country sections. Page numbering is erratic, section headings unstructured and indexing absent. However, layered upon these challenges, are systemic issues of representation arising not only from the independent decisions of a distributed workforce communicating by post and later telegraph but from ambiguities in the information itself, gathered as it was during the turbulent establishment of Western presence. Diplomatic and consular responsibilities were frequently bestowed on company directors, for example, leading to multiple roles; companies' premises provided address and services for other organizations' personnel; continual growth and building construction made job titles and locations short-lived. These irregularities compound already significant challenges for digitization: OCR must overcome distortion, since leaves in middle of 2000-page volumes cannot be made flat; variable print density and print-through on low quality aging paper make identification of characters much harder, as but three examples.

Regardless of these difficulties for contemporary analysis, *The Directories & Chronicles* gathered together remarkably detailed information between its establishment in the mid 19th century right up to 1941, and we provide a history of the serial in the next section. Preoccupation of its original publisher Yorick Murrow with state interference and the lack of transparency which he perceived, especially in respect of successive British administrations, led to publication in the Directories and Chronicles of international treaties, legal announcements and trade agreements which would not otherwise have reached public scrutiny²³. These activities unveil a multilayered undercurrent of tensions which resulted from incompatibilities between both the Western norm of sovereignty and securing of Western privileges on one hand, and hazards of colonial administration on the other. Murrow's project was renewed by subsequent editors well in to the 20th century, and in many respects the governance of emerging global communities might be regarded as a leitmotif of the serial.

Transforming this complex printed material into reliable historical information; yielding actual records of companies, persons and locations and revealing trends across multiple decades and

²² See <https://www.history.ox.ac.uk/global-history-and-microhistory-ahrc-network>.

²³ For a Japanese equivalent of *The Directories & Chronicles* see "The Asia Directory of Manufacturers, Exporters, Merchants and Shippers in Asia" published by The Asia Directory Publishing Company Co, Yokohama, Japan. A survey of similar directories appears in U.S. Department of Commerce, Bureau of Foreign and Domestic Commerce, Trade Information Bulletin No. 841, United States Government Printing Office, Washington 1939.

permitting corroboration with other sources required a new approach. We employ recent developments in scientific annotation to define large numbers of text fragments relating to organizations, locations and persons encountered in the Directories & Chronicles. Collections of annotations provide the foundation for subsequent analyses: producing tokens structured according to schemata out of the inconsistent representations found in the source text. Such stand-off scientific annotation is based on the W3C's Web Annotation Data Model²⁴ (WADM) and we have employed new techniques for its long-term preservation recently developed by CERN and Data Futures.

Creating the millions of annotations necessary for producing empirical evidence from *The Directories & Chronicles* manually is not practical: rather, we employ WADM as a common JSON representation to contain collections of annotations generated by multiple workflows. Analysis of XML resulting from OCR and the output from neural networks, for example, all produce annotations which can all be viewed and maintained using a range of Open Source applications. Manual annotation workflows do play an important role in preliminary structuring of each volume—leading to segmentation of pages for treatment by different automated annotation tools—and for creation of datasets to train neural networks which can subsequently perform automated analysis on a much larger scale. Four aspects of this technical methodology are notable:

- annotations define page fragments (image elements corresponding to annotation 'targets' defined by coordinates) linked to the original page context in which they appear; IIIF enables these fragments to be delivered efficiently into subsequent workflows and presentation applications
- annotation collections are linked using persistent identifiers (PIDs) to the data resources annotated and to contributors, creating a robust long-term preservation mechanism and foundation for cumulative research investment; these collections are serialized in technology-agnostic JSON
- annotation target definitions delineate the characters in underlying OCR generated from page imagery, and this text can be inserted automatically into each annotation for subsequent checking and tokenization
- tokens resulting from analysis of the text defined by each annotation—also represented in JSON—can be organized according to formal schemata and linked to annotations, leading to preservable token payloads which can be managed and preserved using the same infrastructure as annotation collections

This methodology has a number of useful side-effects: one of which is that if, for example, instances of persons identified as annotations contain other unstructured information, such as occupation, full extraction into tokens using controlled vocabularies of roles is not immediately essential. Rather, dictionary-based approaches can rapidly lead to error-free extraction of name and location tokens. Components which can be extracted reliably can be employed in research in the short term, while analysis of more complex information might be postponed. We demonstrate such scenarios in Section 5. This means that data can be incrementally enriched in tokenized data corresponding to each annotation, which remains linked to it and to the original page context. Multiple analyses focussing on different information encapsulated in annotations might lead to multiple schemata and collections of token data.

The information originally gathered in the field by agents of the *Daily Press* then gradually emerges from the serial in its original form, uncluttered by digitization, editorial and production

²⁴ W3C Recommendation 23rd February 2017 - Web Annotation Data Model, <https://www.w3.org/TR/annotation-model/>

compromises, transforming the serial into collections of WADM annotations and structured entity instance tokens—empirical evidence. Enrichment effort can be focussed incrementally on specific research questions and data versioned incrementally into services accessible to the wider research community via interactive repository interfaces (described in Section 5.) and protocols for automated harvesting. This does not constitute a ‘database’ in the conventional sense. Rather, annotations and the token data derived from them are preservable ‘document-oriented’ collections, which are individually self-contained and linked via PIDs to digital sources and contributors. Similarly, infrastructure such as IIF services need not be long-lasting, since equivalent services could be established for future use of the annotation and token collections using technology appropriate at that time. It is therefore possible to build a concise dereferenced version of ADC which does not depend upon external resources for its integrity and can be preserved off line, i.e. without internet-connected dependencies.

4. The Hong Kong Daily Press and emergence of global communication

Appearance of *The Directories & Chronicles* in 1863 was a significant milestone in the evolution of media in Western languages in Asia. Evolving rapidly into a substantial hard-bound publication it was printed and distributed by and clearly benefitted from the extensive reporting network of *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, with which it remained closely connected until the latter’s presses closed in 1941. Superficially at least, its launch can be seen as a product of the burgeoning Chinese media market²⁵. However, *The Directories & Chronicles* was launched in Hong Kong rather than Shanghai—the seat of many other new publications during a period in which the former had become renowned as a center of drug trafficking, gambling, piracy and prostitution. Foundation of the serial amidst Hong Kong’s corruption was hardly consistent with contemporary representation of British commercial interests in Asia, or the development of networks of elites or establishment of one of the most important centers of global trade²⁶. While such a narrative is consistent with the Great Divergence debate, emergence of *The Directories & Chronicles* was in reality an important outcome of the bitter dispute between commercial interests and the British colonial administration in Hong Kong. This surfaced in a “Civil Service Abuses Inquiry” in 1860, better known as the “Caldwell affair”²⁷. The Inquiry escalated beyond the circles of Western possessions in Asia to the British Parliament, and precipitated a conspicuous debate about the reliability of colonial administration.

Yorick Jones Murrow (1815-1884), editor and owner of *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, was a key figure in this debate and a fervent adversary of the British administration in Hong Kong. He was convicted of libel and imprisoned after attacking the Governor in a newspaper article, accusing him of promoting Jardine & Matheson, a powerful corporation and employer of a close relative of the Governor²⁸. This experience did not keep Murrow from pursuing other corruption cases, and his

²⁵ Crow Directories, O’Connor, Peter. *The English-Language Press Networks Of East Asia, 1918-1945* (Leiden, Kent: Global oriental, Brill, 2010).

²⁶ Munn, Christopher. *Anglo-China. Chinese People and British Rule in Hong Kong 1841-1880* (London, New York: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, 2013).

²⁷ Cristopher Munn, Colonialism ‘in a Chinese atmosphere’: the Caldwell affair and the perils of collaboration in early colonial Hong Kong, in: Robert Bickers, Christian Henriot (eds.), *New Frontiers, Imperialism’s New Communities in East Asia, 1842-1953*, Manchester: Manchester University Press, 2000: 12-37.

²⁸ James William Norton-Kyshe, *History of the Laws and Courts of Hongkong. Tracing Consular Jurisdiction in China and Japan and Including Parliamentary Debates, and the Rise, Progress, and Successive Changes in the Various Public Institutions of the Colony from the Earliest Period to the Present Time. With Illustrations. In Two Volumes; Vol. I.*, p740. (London : T. Fisher Unwin, 1902), <https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/100471146>. This information reached the Illustrated London News in 1858.

crusade established a landmark when he attacked the entire colonial administration in a letter to the British Foreign Minister, the Duke of Newcastle in 1861, promising to deliver new evidence to the Civil Services Abuse Inquiry. He demanded public access to governmental archives, which was publicly resisted. Nevertheless the unsigned preface of the first volume of *The Directories & Chronicles* insisted on public access to official documents. Exposing the administration's official Gazette as a source of propaganda, sensationalizing the establishment's legal disputes, and independent publication of international treaties and agreements having sensitive commercial backgrounds²⁹ sustained the reputation of the newspaper as vocal critic of the Hong Kong administration in subsequent decades.

Scant biographical information has emerged about Yorick Murrow³⁰, and much of that arises in an extensive obituary published in *The London and China Express* in 1884³¹. Murrow is portrayed as a businessman whose early career as a representative of Jamieson, How and Co., led to establishment of his own newspaper business. He purchased a former shipping advertising paper, *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, which later claimed³² it had been the first daily newspaper to appear in East Asia. By 1907 the newspaper had reached a daily issue of eight pages, and it presented itself as a global enterprise delivering information and news from Asia to Europe and from Europeans to Asians through a range of products. Since its establishment the newspaper had offered a 24 page weekly compilation of market data and prices from Asian ports, which was delivered rapidly to Europe. This "*China Overland Trade Report*" exploited developing communications and delivered timely news via surface transportation to Alexandria, avoiding the longer journey around the Cape of Good Hope before the opening of the Suez Canal in 1869. Later it accomplished this within 48 hours using submarine cables by establishing a telegraph station at its London office in Fleet Street, the heart of British print media at the time. This station connected to correspondents in European capitals and port cities.³³ Murrow also created a Chinese edition of the *Daily Press*, which offered "the oldest and still immensurable, the best medium for advertisement among the native Community"³⁴. As the fourth pillar of this empire, *The Directories & Chronicles* presented the "marvelous growth of foreign intercourse with China and the other parts of Asia"³⁵. Shipping news

²⁹ Even a rather ill-tempered German review, published in 1917, confirmed that the Directories & Chronicles had published treaties unknown in Germany, although crucial for world politics in East Asia. The reviewer concludes: «Das Directory ist im Allgemeinen auf jedem Bürotisch in Ostasien zu finden. Es sollte auch bei uns in Deutschland bekannter werden». Wolf v. Dewall, 'Reviewed Work(s): The Directory and Chronicle for China, Japan, Corea, Indo-China, Straits Settlements, Malay States, Siam, Netherlands India, Borneo, the Philippines Etc. For the Year 1916 by; The China Year Book 1916 by H. T. Montague Bell and H. G. W. Woodhead', *Weltwirtschaftliches Archiv*, 9 (1917), 84–86.

³⁰ Christopher Munn, in *Dictionary of Hong Kong Biography*, May Holdsworth, Christopher Munn (Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2011).

³¹ Mentioned in Norton-Kyshe, *The History of the Laws and Courts of Hong Kong: Tracing Consular Jurisdiction in China and Japan and Including Parliamentary Debates: And the Rise, Progress, and Successive Changes in the Various Public Institutions of the Colony from the Earliest Period to the Present Time*. See article in *Hong Kong Daily Press* 1884-04-24: "He leaves a widow (his second wife) and six children."

³² *The Hong Kong Daily Press* Jubilee publication, *The Hong Kong Daily Press 1907-10-01*: 2. For coverage by foreign language newspapers we have employed the collection of the Hong Kong Public Libraries (<https://mmis.hkpl.gov.hk/old-hk-collection>) and the online archive of Singapore's newspapers (<https://eresources.nlb.gov.sg/newspapers/>).

³³ Arnold Wright, *Twentieth Century Impressions of Hong-Kong, Shanghai, and Other Treaty Ports of China. Their History, People, Commerce, Industries, and Resources* (London: London Lloyd's Greater Britain Pub. Co, 1908) : 350.

³⁴ Ibid. The founder of the Chinese edition of the *Daily Press*, Wong Shing, was later the director of the first Chinese owned newspaper in Hong Kong. See Edward J.M Rhoads, *Dictionary of Hong Kong Biography*, May Holdsworth, Christopher Munn, eds. (Hong Kong: Hong Kong University Press, 2011): 454.

³⁵ *Jubilee of the "Hongkong Daily Press", 1857-1907, The Hong Kong Daily Press 1907-10-01*: 9.

remained central—the publisher measured development of Hong Kong in terms of growing capacity of the port; ship numbers, cargo diversity and increasing tonnage.

Yorick Murrow left Asia during 1867 and retired to Jersey and later to London, but remained the owner of the publisher until his death in 1884. Thereafter, his Hong Kong-based newspapers and *The Directories & Chronicles* remained under the control of his family through a limited company. *The London and China Express* obituary portrayed him as a fervent talent in the new profession of journalism, attributing to Murrow considerable influence and power: “As a journalist he exercised publicly that dominant influence on local opinion which had been one of his chief characteristics in private life.” With “fearless courage, energy and perseverance” he was believed to have fought against “the abuses which seem inseparable from the founding of every British Colony”³⁶.

After Murrow’s death the publisher gradually privileged economic success over the earlier ideological focus of the *Daily Press*. *The Directories & Chronicles* cultivated its new market sector and sold Asian trading information with almost unbroken success despite political upheavals, World War I and the early conflicts preceding World War II during the 1930s. Hong Kong remained the hub and the political center of the publisher, although the profile of its management changed substantially. Murrow’s widow, Mary (1853-1937)³⁷ became proprietor until 1889, and from 1890 onwards the family leased the company to D. Warres-Smith. Among Murrow’s successors Warres-Smith’s activities are the most difficult to trace, though he had worked at the *Daily Press* office in Hong Kong in 1889 and clearly knew the business first-hand. Significantly, he started selling information derived from the Directories & Chronicles in a format targeting a more European public than the publisher’s traditional British-imperial consumers. At the turn of the century this was an economically prudent decision. Media in Asia had multiplied³⁸ and Lloyd’s of London had established its *Greater Britain Publishing Company*. In 1900 the so-called Boxer rebellion brought the armies of eight Western states to China, and the Boxer protocols forced open the Chinese market, evoking an atmosphere which has been described as a gold rush. Warres-Smith recognized the potential for profiting and published a version of *The Directories & Chronicles* aimed at European settlements in Asia³⁹. These volumes, today ‘rare books’ digitized in the 1990s and now available in at least ten different versions, would hardly pass a plagiarism test—their structure and text were almost identical to that of *The Directories & Chronicles* without referring to it.

Before the onset of World War I a new director replaced Warres-Smith. Henry Adolphus Cartwright arrived in November 1914 and remained at the publisher for ten years⁴⁰. Once more the business had a charismatic public figurehead, and when he died from typhoid fever in 1925, his obituary presented a cosmopolitan with previous editorial experience in Buenos Aires with Lloyd’s Greater

³⁶ The Hong Kong Daily Press reprinted substantial parts of the obituary. *The Hong Kong Daily Press* 1884-04-24.

³⁷ Mary Murrow appears in the 1891 England Census, listed at 136, Abingdon Rd, Kensington, London, born in Karachi, British-India and described as British subject, 37 years old.

³⁸ See *Newspaper Directory of China, Including Hongkong*, Carl Crow Inc. Shanghai, 1931 for example and *The English-Language Press Networks Of East Asia, 1918-1945* already in reference 24.

³⁹ D. Warres-Smith and Charles William Wason, *European Settlements in the Far East; China, Japan, Corea, Indo-China, Straits Settlements, Malay States, Siam, Netherlands, India, Borneo, the Philippines, Etc.*, xii, p331. (London: S. Low, Marston & company, 1900), available <https://archive.org/details/cu31924014072791/page/n11>

⁴⁰ See Arnold Wright, *Twentieth century impressions of Hong-kong, Shanghai, and other Treaty Ports of China, their history, people, commerce, industries, and resources*, London Greater Britain Pub. Co, 1908, <https://archive.org/details/twentiethcentury00wriguoft/page/788>.

Britain Publishing Company. Cartwright had been a Free Mason and a politically active citizen of Hong Kong. He was moreover a member of the Constitutional Reform Association⁴¹ and engaged with some of the most crucial social political questions of his time, such as child labor and the status of the “mui tsai”⁴². Both of these topics intertwined Chinese national issues with international politics through the League of Nations and the International Labor Organization. A decade of uncertainty followed: Cartwright was succeeded by O.T. Breakspear, who left Hong Kong at the end of 1928 and was followed at the *The Hong Kong Daily Press* by D. J. Evans and shortly afterwards in 1931 by R.T. Barnett.

From 1933 onwards, a family member, Henry Lloyd Murrow took up the business. He was born in 1879 and arrived in Hong Kong after a military career, having served in the South African Wars and in World War I. After a childhood in Jersey this Murrow appears in British election registers of the 1930s at a Chelsea address in London: a man of the British Empire on the brink of its extinction. He had married in Delhi in 1908 and died in Hong Kong in 1951. Records from the 1930s confirm that Henry Murrow was an established member of Hong Kong society. He addressed British industry at the Hong Kong Rotary Club in 1932⁴³, and was the president of the Mamak Hockey Tournament in 1935⁴⁴. A newspaper article on his daughter’s wedding to Lieut. Ronald Harrison of the British Navy left no doubt about the family’s social status⁴⁵. He addressed the Y’s Men’s Club in 1938, praising the discipline of Chinese soldiers⁴⁶ and enlarged what had become a media empire with a quarterly entitled *Changing China*, which launched in 1934 with a generous editorial staff.

5. Infrastructure, Analysis and Preliminary Results

5.1 Technical Infrastructure

The infrastructure which we have developed to analyse this source is based on a digital collection of high resolution images obtained by scanning each page of the printed serial, plus OCR-XML which includes per-character position and confidence information. The Data Futures *freizo*⁴⁷ platform was used to manage this process as well as the resulting digital collection, and also for subsequent development of workflows and generation of repositories. Individual page assets comprise approximately 20MB of image files in TIFF format plus 10MB XML, and this data is temporarily stored on S3, Amazon’s commercial storage service. Metadata, including history of all changes and research community account management, is replicated automatically by *freizo* in a minimum of three database members residing on leased linux virtual machines (VMs) in different physical locations. IIIF services residing on separate leased VMs are generated from the digital page collection and these services supply imagery for multiple research workflows and internet presentations. Routine annotation and internet presentation requirements are satisfied by a single

⁴¹ Death of Mr. H.A. Cartwright, Well-known Editor succumbs to typhoid, *The Hong Kong Telegraph*, 1925-01-27.

⁴² Mr. H. A. Cartwright dead, *The China Mail*, 1925-01-27.

⁴³ Rotary Club Address, *The Hong Kong Telegraph* 1932-11-30.

⁴⁴ *The Hong Kong Telegraph* 1935-10-23.

⁴⁵ Brilliant Ceremony at Cathedral, *The Hong Kong Daily Press*, 1937-01-08.

⁴⁶ Timely Talk to Y’s Men’s Club by Lt.-Col. Murrow, *The Hong Kong Daily Press* 1938-07-22.

⁴⁷ See <https://www.data-futures.org/freizo.html> - *freizo* is a research workflow and corpus migration platform which uses MongoDB.

IIIF server. However, a number of manual annotation activities in which concurrent contractor or student user numbers exceed a few 10s, have required multiple IIIF services, which provide performance improvements through parallelization. Duplicating IIIF servers also provides greater reliability: the cost and delay arising from regenerating a IIIF service from TIFF imagery (as opposed to replicating one already providing reliable service) has become significant. Retaining multiple copies of TIFF image and OCR data—approximately 8TB—represents a significant operating cost, and the project envisages replicating and maintaining two IIIF services permanently, and moving the TIFF imagery to near-line storage. The latter forms the basis of digital preservation of the complete serial as part of an independent strategy which we do not address in detail here. We currently use Linear Tape Open (LTO) storage technology, which program has emerged from a commercial dispute at the time of writing, and this now makes it possible to store TIFF imagery and OCR data on single tape cartridges having an approximate lifetime of twenty years. Previously it would have been necessary to span multiple tape volumes, introducing restoration complexity and elevating vulnerability.

The project's IIIF services support interactive requirements such as browsing at high resolution for multiple viewing platform sizes and delivering individual page images or image fragments, such as those defined by annotations, into a range of workflows and external analysis instruments (see the *freizo* and Invenio examples below). For example, IIIF-compatible image-viewing applications such as Mirador and Cantaloupe can be used to search and browse annotations, whether generated automatically or manually. Annotation metadata for active research is managed using *freizo*—which maintains links between annotations, and source material and supports researchers' Open Researcher and Contributor IDs (ORCID) for contributor verification and permission-based access control. Metadata is also preserved using Invenio-based repositories created using *freizo*, as an initial deposit plus subsequent versioning. At the time of writing Zenodo⁴⁸ IIIF implementation is not comprehensive. We deposit annotation and other project metadata in Zenodo as JSON files (see following discussion) and in addition we maintain Invenio-3 repositories using the *hasdai*⁴⁹ infrastructure which integrates IIIF and supports discovery via Elasticsearch (<https://www.elastic.co/>).

5.2 Analysis

As outlined in Section 3. we employ both manual and machine methods to produce annotation collections—which are represented as WADM using JSON. Tokenized information extracted from the text defined by the annotations, as well as schemata describing such tokens are also represented using JSON. In the next sections we present two examples based on the foreign resident listings of the serial using this methodology. The first illustrates tokenization via a *freizo* workflow and is concerned with information related to individual persons' occupations, and it demonstrates Elasticsearch within an Invenio repository generated from the annotation and token collections. The second example employs geographic visualization of the same annotation and token dataset—the Foreign Residents Benchmark (FRB) dataset—made in to a Zenodo deposit. Access to both of these data resources is unrestricted and, although they are currently sub-sets of our work on the full serial, it is evident that they might support wider inquiries than the preliminary analyses presented here.

⁴⁸ Zenodo is a catch-all repository implemented using the Invenio software framework and funded by CERN, The European Commission and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation. See <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

⁴⁹ *hasdai* is a network of distributed Invenio-3 repositories developed by the *hasdai* partnership and CERN. See <https://hasdai.org/>.

5.1.1 Tracing Individual Persons

The illustration below shows a page fragment, delivered by the IIF service into a *freizo* workflow. The fragment has previously been defined as an annotation via analysis of the OCR-XML produced from a page of the serial. This annotation takes the form of a target specification ('xywh' in the illustration) linked to 'body' metadata. To view the annotation with others on the page a IIF application such as Mirador⁵⁰ is required. *freizo* generates a number of versions of annotation metadata, since WADM itself is not recognized by Mirador, which at the time of writing requires a specific version of Open Annotation Data Model (OADM) derived from the former. In this example an OCR error ('Pours' versus 'Tours') has been detected based on XML confidence data, a context-sensitive dictionary and surrounding entries, since the listing is organized alphabetically, and the person instance has been put in a queue for manual approval of the automated recommendation. Additionally, a dictionary of terms developed to detect and structure diplomatic and consular activities has been applied in this example to tokenize the person instance string—producing a token collection against a schema to support a specific research activity (see below). The dictionary 'hits' are visible below the raw OCR string, and 'current parse' shows the tokens established (note that the actual IIF crop showing 'British Consulate, Shanghai' extends beyond the right extent of this illustration but can be viewed in FRB online). This process generates tokens reflecting occupation and location, independent of the order of appearance of matched text in the original string.

Asset No	574903
Crop	
OCR String	'Pours, B. G., vice-consul (shipping), British Consulate, Shanghai
chunk id	1544_117,1258,1077,40
confidence	20
fuzz	0
hits	consul:diprole;British:nation;Consulate:diporg;
page	1544
xywh	117,1258,1077,40
line	33
Processed by (uid)	10127
Processed by (name)	Michael Offermann
tokenizer version	1.1
current parse	
field	surname
value	Tours
field	forename
value	B. G.
field	occupation
value	vice-consul (shipping)
field	organization
value	British Consulate
field	location
value	Shanghai

The FRB dataset comprises foreign resident person instances reported in the serial for two periods which are of crucial importance for the colonial history of East Asia—covering the consequences of the First Sino-Japanese War and the political tensions before the Second Sino-Japanese War. In addition to their geopolitical relevance, these two periods are particularly significant for the way in which foreign residents shaped privilege-based societies until they disappeared from East Asia⁵¹. In

⁵⁰ Mirador is an open-source, web based, multi-window image viewing platform enabling comparison and annotation of IIF image resources. See <https://projectmirador.org/>.

⁵¹ Bickers, Robert A. *Out of China: How the Chinese Ended the Era of Western Domination* (London: Penguin, 2018).

the following we test these historiographical assumptions using this dataset. The First Sino-Japanese War, waged from July 1894 to April 1895, was followed by re-establishment of communities of foreign residents in East Asia. In the early 20th century movement of Westerners to larger communities in coastal cities was followed by a marked exodus during escalating conflict in the Second Sino-Japanese War between July 1937 and September 1945, which some sources date to the Japanese invasion of Manchuria in 1931. The serial lists the following numbers of instances of persons in these years:

1896	13,890
1899	16,025
1934	19,640
1937	11,754

The FRB dataset comprises annotation and token data collections relating to foreign residents for each of these years. An Invenio repository generated by *freizo* using FRB which fully supports IIF as is accessible at <https://fr-benchmark.unibas.hasdai.org>, and this presents the tokenized person instances linked to annotations as primary research assets. The following illustration, developing the example above, shows multiple persons with surname ‘Tours’ returned by Invenio’s implementation of the Elasticsearch engine. Selecting the 1896 instance (see final Invenio illustration) shows Tours, B. G. listed as a student at the British Legation in Peking. In contrast, in the *freizo* illustration, above (which which addresses the 1903 volume), Tours occupation is ‘vice-consul (shipping)’, while in 1899 we find a Tours, B. G. as assistant at the Legation in Peking. We can be relatively confident it is the same person, first as a student and then as assistant in Peking before being posted to Shanghai (exceptionally, for the purpose of this publication we have included the 1903 instance of Tours, B.G. in the FRB dataset). While Tours, B.G. is simply an example and but a few years are considered using FRB, by using the complete foreign resident data we can now trace tens of thousands of persons’ careers in this way. We defer discussion about ascription of these person instance observations to canonical person entities to a future publication. The final Invenio illustration also shows both display of the body of the annotation within Invenio using the same IIF as *freizo* and a ‘View in Mirador’ link, which provides interactive access to this person instance on the page of the serial where it appeared.

This example supports a DODIS-EIB collaborative project⁵² examining persons with both diplomatic/consular and commercial responsibilities. Although FRB addresses only persons’ locations, processing the additional text relating to persons’ occupations appearing in the foreign residents listings, as shown in the *freizo* workflow for 1903, enables token data collections to be generated which represent personnel with diplomatic and consular responsibilities present in East Asia, nation by nation, year upon year.

⁵² Diplomatic Documents of Switzerland, DODIS (<https://www.dodis.ch>): see <https://swiss-diplo.ch/projekt/>.

location

- Peking (2)
- British North Borneo (1)
- Shanghai (1)

year

- 1899 (2)
- 1896 (1)
- 1903 (1)

Found 4 results.

Tours, B. G.

Peking
1896

Tours, B. G.

Peking
1899

Tours, B. G.

Shanghai
1903

Tours, D.

British North Borneo
1899

Tours, B. G.

Tours, B. G., student, British Legation, Peking

Honourific:

Surname: [Tours](#)

Forename: B. G.

Locaton: [Peking](#)

Year: [1896](#)

Page: 1120

Position: 150,235,802,38

[View in mirador](#)

Powered by [Invenio](#)

5.1 Visualizing the International Community

We now turn instead to the claim of *The Hong Kong Daily Press* for coverage by the serial of commercial activity and foreign residents affairs throughout the whole of East Asia. An open-access version of the FRB dataset has been created as a deposit with the international Zenodo repository, which can be downloaded via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2580997>. We have rendered the dataset on to maps, independent of other technologies, or infrastructure such as the IIF service. Two of these maps—1896 & 1937— appear in the following illustrations and an explanatory PDF document with additional maps can be downloaded. The FRB Zenodo deposit is self-describing and technology-agnostic—requiring no existing software to enable anonymous persons or machines in the future to examine and fully employ it. Zenodo’s ‘Annotation Collection’ datatype, developed in a collaboration between CERN and Data Futures, has been employed, making it easier for automated applications to discover and evaluate the dataset.

It is evident from these visualizations that within the timeframe covered by FRB the foreign resident population is transformed from tiny communities spread thinly over a vast territory (above) to much larger communities along coastlines during the 1930s—even as these were diminishing towards the end of the decade before World War II. We do not depict highways or railroad construction in these basic visualizations, but the expansion of small communities of Westerners during the 1890s provides evidence, for example, of construction of a new transport route from the

Dairen peninsula (modern Dalian) towards Harbin⁵³. Significantly, while Harbin had attracted a large population of foreign residents by the 1930s, intermediate communities along this route diminished. This is notable—underlining reluctance of the serial to recognize the proclamation of Manchukuo as a Japanese dependency in 1932. *The Directories & Chronicles* lists it instead as “Manchurian Trade Centers”⁵⁴. The distribution of foreign resident communities reported by the Directories and Chronicles gives us access to this confrontation between two forms of colonialism in East Asia. Namely collision of the formal colonization which Japan pursued in the 1930s, with the more disorderly Western model of informal trading networks established and managed by foreign residents from the mid 19th century. This international community model derived its effectiveness not so much from territorial possession as from network development—gradually developing relationships with local counterparts and connecting small social groups with major centers of trade. The tiny far-flung communities we see in the 1896 visualization are nodes of this network and their subsequent relocation belies a fundamental shift in commercial practice during this period.

Rendered in this way the FRB dataset also permits another observation which would be difficult to demonstrate without such empirical evidence. It is clear from comparison of the detail in the lower right of the two visualizations, that the change in distribution of communities in the Straits

⁵³ For Harbin and its foreign communities see Frank Grüner, *The Chicago of the East – Cross-Border Activities and Transnational Biographies of Adventurers, Shady Characters, and Criminals in the Cosmopolitan City of Harbin*, (*Comparativ - Zeitschrift für Globalgeschichte und vergleichende Gesellschaftsforschung* 23(6) 2013: 52-75, <https://www.comparativ.net/v2/article/view/1747>).

⁵⁴ *The Directory & Chronicle of China, Japan, Korea, Indo-China, Straits Settlements, Malaya, Siam, Netherlands India, Borneo, The Philippines, &c.*, page A96, *The Hong Kong Daily Press Ltd.* 1937.

Settlements contrasts sharply with locations of foreign resident communities in the rest of East Asia. There are *more* small inland communities in 1937 compared with 1896—the opposite of the transformation we observe in the rest of East Asia comparing the two periods relating to the Sino-Japanese war.

This is remarkable, since British interests did not dominate the channel connecting the Indian and the Pacific Oceans, which remains today geopolitically very heterogeneous and in the early 20th century included multiple forms of foreign and indigenous governance, claims and rules. It is a unique territory in which different generations of colonial rule confronted one another: old Portuguese and Dutch possessions were in close proximity with the newer British, French and US dependencies—and these all overlaid more ancient Chinese and Arabic trading routes. Instead of the pervasive influence of the British Empire these visualizations present highly international activity in the Straits of Malacca and Singapore throughout the late 19th century and in to the 1930s. Heretofore these territories have been rather neglected by historical research, although the Straits represents an important opportunity to harness the cross-border potential of global history. From this brief analysis it is evident that an independent network of foreign residents was pivotal in shaping this region, and its evolution should not simply be understood as an expression of imperial policies. We can now embark on tracing the companies which the individuals in these communities represented and search for external evidence of their nationalities.

We claim that this digital methodology permits such conclusions to arise naturally from the information originally gathered in the serial. Murrow's achievement in transmitting and preserving this information was ground-breaking, but at the time the volumes of the serial could not be analyzed in this way. Redelivered digitally, the Directories and Chronicles display dynamic social interactions: they create a *society* of foreign residents which has not previously been accessible.

6. Conclusions

In 1863 an annual publication of *The Hong Kong Daily Press* defied convention and took on colonial politics to represent Western commercial projects and foreign resident communities across East Asia. However the steadily expanding flow of information which the *The Directories & Chronicles* delivered has so far evaded scholarly research: it has not been available as a complete serial, in which form its real potential as a source for historians might be realized. Moreover, access to its large volumes and irregular layers of information necessitates a new digital methodology, rather than analogue criticism or versions of existing digital techniques. The theoretical framework of a micro-global history allows us to focus on the historicity of actors, and data-driven historiography has proved to be promising for providing insights beyond contemporary colonial, national and imperial approaches. Using the combination of manual and machinic annotation described here, a framework of information connected to the printed serial has been created. Structured data tokens processed from these annotations, and organized by inquiry-specific schemata reveal a new and fascinating matrix of coincidences beyond the continuous flow of information presumed by the original serial.

The Directories and Chronicles were compiled as a statistical overview, documenting arrivals and departures and conducting surveys as part of the mainstream daily activities of the *The Hong Kong Daily Press*. Redelivered as annotation collections this data regains an analytical quality, which is distinct in important ways from contemporary notions of 'big data'. Although derived from the same raw information as might be employed by data mining methods, the annotations produced

here are not fragments isolated from their context. Instead of following the contemporary rationale, historiography in the digital age can examine consequences unforeseen in the 19th and 20th centuries — we can test new questions with this data.

The foreign resident benchmark dataset, which we have used to illustrate this methodology, demonstrates transnational social spaces in East Asia during this period. While hardly exhaustive as a census, a yearly average of fifteen thousand instances of named individuals' locations from multiple Western nations gathered by *The Hong Kong Daily Press* provides clear empirical evidence for hundreds of foreign resident communities. These persons are distributed between diplomatic functions, the military, religious organizations, major corporations such as banks and engineering conglomerates and a host of smaller companies. Communities of ten or less individuals, often more than 500 km from larger settlements, significantly outnumber larger communities in the 19th century, and this distribution persists into the 1910s. The project of *The Hong Kong Daily Press* was not to enhance British-dominated access to the colonial market. On the contrary its founder, Yorick Murrow, was interested in networks formed among foreign residents of multiple nationalities and with their local trading partners: *against* rather than in support of the British government. In the FRB dataset we see the tenure and movements of individuals comprising these networks for the first time; an encouraging indication that a digital historiography can transcend the narrative of divergence and challenge the national focus on colonial relations. Murrow's insight into the significance of emerging transnational communities and his investment in this serial has preserved the wealth of information gathered by *The Hong Kong Daily Press* and given us valuable tools for understanding the dynamics of East Asia.